

Transforming Mage AI Workflows into Standardized CWL and Python Pipelines

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Abstract—Mage AI provides a powerful platform for designing and executing data pipelines. Still, its integration with workflow standards such as the Common Workflow Language (CWL) and Python-based workflows is essential to ensure reproducibility, portability, and compatibility. This paper introduces a methodology for converting Mage workflows into CWL and Python standard flows using custom scripts and transformation logic. We detail the implementation, the challenges addressed, and the broader implications of this approach while situating it within the wider context of workflow management and execution. The experimental results demonstrate significant performance improvements that validate the benefits of adopting this approach in real-world scenarios.

I. INTRODUCTION

Workflow management systems are essential tools in data processing, scientific research, and cloud-based computing, as they enable the automation, coordination, and optimization of complex workflows. These systems help streamline data pipelines, ensure reproducibility, and enhance scalability by efficiently managing dependencies, scheduling tasks, and integrating various tools and frameworks. By reducing manual intervention and minimizing errors, workflow management systems improve efficiency, making them indispensable for handling large-scale data processing and deploying robust cloud-based applications.

Apache Airflow [1] provides robust workflow orchestration for large enterprises, enabling the management of complex, distributed pipelines. Similarly, Nextflow [2] is tailored for scientific computing and informatics, offering powerful, standardized workflow management. However, both of these platforms typically require extensive setup and configuration, making them more suitable for technically advanced environments.

In contrast, Mage AI [3] is a lightweight, open-source data pipeline tool designed with ease of use in mind. Its intuitive user interface makes it accessible for everyone—from seasoned developers to beginners—allowing users to quickly create, execute, and manage pipelines for tasks such as data

loading, transformation, and export without the need for complex configurations. This user-friendly approach simplifies the process of designing data pipelines, ensuring that users with varying levels of technical expertise can effectively leverage the platform.

Despite these varied strengths, the landscape of workflow management tools remains fragmented because many tools use their own language to describe workflows. This lack of standardization can limit collaboration and hinder portability across systems [4]. To address these issues, initiatives such as the Common Workflow Language (CWL) [5] have been introduced. CWL standardizes the description of workflows by (i) separating the specification of workflow tools from their execution, (ii) supporting key principles such as automation, scalability, abstraction, provenance, portability, and reusability, and (iii) fostering an open-source, community-driven approach. By providing a common framework, CWL has the potential to bridge the gap between the powerful, yet complex, orchestration tools like Apache Airflow and Nextflow and the accessible, intuitive design offered by Mage AI.

The goal of this paper is to combine the intuitive user interface of Mage AI with a standardized method for creating workflows that remain easy to design, portable, and shareable across different parties. Users of any experience level can first develop pipelines using Mage AI, which is a more pleasant experience, and subsequently convert them into standardized workflows, making them easier to share with others. To achieve this, we present a semi-automated conversion process that transforms Mage AI pipelines into a standardized workflow language. We have selected the Common Workflow Language (CWL) as our target standard because it is one of the most widely adopted open standards for workflow management systems. CWL is technology-agnostic and can execute virtually any process running on a computer, including tasks within Docker containers.

The contributions of this paper are summarized as follows:

- Develop a semi-to-fully automated conversion algorithm that transforms Mage AI pipelines into CWL-compatible workflows. This is achieved in two steps:(i) First the Mage AI backend is used to manage Python scripts tasked with automatic removal of Mage AI-specific information from the pipeline; and (ii) automatically generate corresponding CWL workflows for each script while establishing the necessary logic to transfer data between them.
- Ensure the creation of a dedicated Python environment for installing dependencies.
- Provide a comprehensive list of challenges and proposed mitigations to solve such challenges faced during the process of the conversion of the Mage AI process into CWL.
- Discuss possible practical applications and future work in this direction.

A. State of the Art

Recent advances in workflow management and standardization have focused on enabling interoperability, scalability, and reproducibility. In the following, we outline some of the key systems in this space.

- **Common Workflow Language:** An open standard for defining portable workflows, CWL is widely used in bioinformatics and data science due to its compatibility with various execution backends.
- **CWL-WES [6]:** A cloud-native solution that executes CWL workflows via GA4GH (Global Alliance for Genomics and Health) Workflow Execution Service (WES) APIs. CWL-WES integrates with Task Execution Service (TES) backends such as TESK [7], offering scalable, standards-compliant workflow execution.
- **Mage AI Integration Challenges:** Although Mage AI excels at designing data pipelines, it lacks native CWL support. This shortcoming can be problematic for organizations requiring standardized workflows for reproducibility and collaboration.
- **KNIME-CWL:** This initiative bridges user-friendly workflow environments (such as KNIME) with CWL, allowing KNIME workflows to run in distributed setups. It illustrates how intuitive design tools can be combined with standardized execution backends [8].
- **CWL-Airflow:** CWL-Airflow pairs CWL’s portability with Apache Airflow’s orchestration capabilities, enabling scalable execution of CWL workflows within Airflow’s Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) framework. It manages dependencies, scheduling, and fault tolerance, and offers extensive monitoring and debugging. [9] presents the methodology of CWL-Airflow.
- **CNT (CWL-Nextflow Translation):** In contrast to approaches that unify workflows under a single standard (like CWL), [10] introduces a semi-automated method translates CWL to Nextflow, specifically addressing genomic pipelines.

Despite significant advancements in workflow management systems, a critical gap remains in bridging user-friendly design platforms, like Mage AI, with standardized execution frameworks, such as CWL. Current solutions like CWL-Airflow and KNIME-CWL demonstrate the potential for integrating intuitive pipeline editors with portable, reproducible workflows. However, these systems often require significant manual configuration, lack seamless transformation processes, or are limited in their ability to scale across diverse environments. Mage AI’s intuitive interface provides an excellent starting point for designing pipelines but falls short in supporting the portability, reproducibility, and standardization offered by CWL.

Table I compares the features of Mage AI, CWL-Airflow, and KNIME-CWL, focusing on usability, standardization, scalability, portability, error handling, data visualization, and execution speed. This comparison underscores the need for a methodology that bridges Mage AI’s user-friendly interface—which simplifies data processing even for novice data scientists—and CWL’s robust reproducibility and portability.

TABLE I. COMPARISON OF WORKFLOW MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS

Feature	Mage AI	CWL-Airflow	KNIME-CWL
User Interface	Intuitive GUI	YAML configuration	Visual workflow editor
CWL Support	No support	Full support	Partial support
Scalability	Limited	Highly scalable with Airflow	Scalable with KNIME Server
Portability	Low	High	Medium
Error Handling	Basic	Advanced	Intermediate
Data Visualization	Built-in	External tools needed	Built-in
Execution Speed	Moderate	High	Moderate

II. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The transformation process consists of two primary steps: converting Mage blocks into Python scripts and generating CWL files for standardized execution. This section will outline the algorithm responsible for this conversion, which translates Mage-style blocks into plain Python scripts and constructs the corresponding CWL descriptions to represent the same workflow as in Mage.

Fig. 1. Mage to CWL conversion workflow

Figure 1 illustrates the conversion process from a Mage AI pipeline to its CWL representation. This process involves the sequential application of two algorithms, which will be described in detail in the following sections, on the Mage AI pipeline and its intermediate representation, which consists solely of Python scripts, excluding any Mage AI-specific code, while also omitting the complete CWL representation and its associated configuration files for the workflows.

A. Mage to Python transformation algorithm

The algorithm 1 is the most important part of the transformation process from a Mage pipeline to CWL. The algorithm comprises transformations applied to the code, using AST (Abstract Syntax Tree) to remove different parts of the code that are specific to Mage, and transfer the block from a function call to a `'if __name__ == "__main__"'` Python script that can be executed directly from the command line. The algorithm's complexity is $O(n)$, increasing linearly with each added block.

This algorithm ensures that Mage AI pipelines are converted into standalone Python scripts. By removing Mage-specific dependencies and adapting the code into a format that can be executed independently, this step makes the workflows portable and prepares them for integration into CWL workflows. The resulting Python scripts are foundational for achieving compatibility with standardized execution environments.

Algorithm 1: MageToPython Code Transformation

```

Input: code_string: Mage AI formatted Python code,
block_name: Current block name,
repo_name: Repository name,
previous_block_name (optional): Previous block name
Output: code_string: Transformed Python code,
env_vars: Extracted environment variables

1 Function FormatCodeAutopepEight():
2   Create a temporary file with code_string;
3   Format the file using autopep8;
4   Read the formatted code back into code_string;
5   Handle exceptions and delete the temporary file;
6 end
7 Function FormatCodeBlack():
8   Create a temporary file with code_string;
9   Format the file using black library;
10  Read the formatted code back into code_string;
11  Handle exceptions and delete the temporary file;
12 end
13 Function RemoveMageImports():
14  Parse the code_string into an Abstract Syntax Tree (AST);
15  Initialize MageToPythonTransformer with relevant parameters:
16    - word, decorators, block_name, previous_block_name;
17  Visit the AST using the transformer to remove imports, unused code, and
18    Mage AI-specific decorators;
19  Check for if __name__ == '__main__' structure;
20  if not present then
21    | Add an if __name__ == '__main__' block;
22  end if
23  Insert statements collected from the decorated function by the transformer
24    into the if __name__ block and keep everything the same;
25  Add required imports (os, pandas) if missing;
26  Unparse the modified AST back into Python code;
27  Remove unused code and imports from the Python code using the
28    RemoveUnusedCode utility;
29  Return the cleaned code and the extracted environment variables;
30 end
31 Function MageToPython():
32  Call RemoveMageImports();
33  Call FormatCodeAutopepEight();
34  Call FormatCodeBlack();
35 end
36 return code_string, env_vars

```

B. Mage to CWL transformation algorithm

The second part of the transformation process after converting all the blocks from a Mage pipeline to plain Python is done in algorithm 2. This algorithm wraps the previously converted Python scripts in CWL workflows based on three kinds of templates if the block is the first in the hierarchy, is in the middle, or is the last one.

Besides the workflows for the blocks, there will be a main workflow that will call the previous ones in sequence and will include some configurations, such as environment variables, that are specific to the pipeline.

At the end of the algorithm, all workflows, which are YAML files, are included alongside the converted Python scripts and a shell script that will validate and run the CWL pipeline in a ZIP file that will be provided for download. The complexity of this algorithm is also $O(n)$.

Algorithm 2: MageToCWL Transformation Process

```

Input: blocks: List of workflow blocks,
pipeline_name: Name of the pipeline,
repo_name: Name of the repository
Output: files: Dictionary containing CWL and Python files

1 Function TransformMageToPython():
2   foreach block  $b_i$  in blocks do
3     if  $i = 0$  then
4       | Initialize MageToPython with block.content,
5       |   block.uuid;
6     end if
7     else
8       | Initialize MageToPython with previous block name;
9     end if
10    Call mage_to_python and append result to results;
11  end foreach
12 end
13 Function Process():
14  Call TransformMageToPython();
15  Initialize inputs and workflow templates;
16  Add result_displayer.py and run.sh scripts to files;
17  foreach result  $r_i$  in results do
18    Add Python script to files;
19    Update inputs and workflow for  $r_i$ ;
20    if  $i = 0$  then
21      // This function calls the code to create
22      // the CWL template for the first block in
23      // the workflow, which only has outputs
24      Use FirstStepTemplate();
25    end if
26    else if  $i = \text{len}(\text{results}) - 1$  then
27      // This function calls the code to create
28      // the CWL template for the last block in
29      // the workflow, which needs to output the
30      // final result in a readable way
31      Use LastStepTemplate();
32      Define workflow outputs;
33    end if
34    else
35      // This function will return the CWL
36      // template for any other block that is
37      // not the first or the last, and only
38      // needs to get the result from the
39      // previous block and pass it to the next
40      // one
41      Use StepTemplate();
42    end if
43    Add step to workflow;
44  end foreach
45  Serialize inputs and workflow to YAML files;
46 end
47 return files

```

C. Implementation Details

This subsection will go a little more in depth on the code, written in Python, and will give some details about the two main classes involved in the transformation workflow, from Mage AI to Python and from Python to CWL. The entire code can be found in https://github.com/JarcauCristian/MageAPI/tree/main/mage_to_cwl.

1) *MageToPython Class*: The `MageToPython` class is responsible for converting Mage blocks into standalone Python scripts. Key features include leveraging the Mage API to access all blocks in the pipeline along with their associated code. The retrieved code is stored as a string, facilitating easy processing. In addition, the name of the previous block is required to identify the source block for the data that is being emitted.

The main processing steps performed by this class are as follows:

- **Code Formatting**: Uses `autopep8` and `black` for consistent formatting.
- **Environment Variables**: Translates Mage-specific variables into standard Python `os.getenv()` calls.
- **Dependency Removal**: Removes Mage-specific imports and patterns for compatibility.

The definition of the Python class can be found here: https://github.com/JarcauCristian/MageAPI/blob/main/mage_to_cwl/mage_to_python.py.

2) *MageToCWL Class*: The `MageToCWL` class orchestrates the transformation of Mage blocks, which are already converted to classic Python scripts, into CWL workflows. Below is an overview of its core functions.

- **Initialization**: Validations step for the output of `MageToPython` class, and initialization of the folder structure that will be compressed into a zip file, that will contain all the necessary files.
- **Transformation**: Converts Mage blocks into Python scripts and CWL tool definitions using templates.
- **Workflow Assembly**: Constructs the CWL workflow by linking individual steps and managing input/output dependencies.

The definition of the Python class can be found here: https://github.com/JarcauCristian/MageAPI/blob/main/mage_to_cwl/mage_to_cwl.py.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

An experiment was conducted in which two pipelines were converted from Mage AI to CWL. Both pipeline representations were executed five times each, and the average execution time was measured to compare their performance.

Given that CWL is widely used in genomic research and other medical-related fields, the *Bowtie* pipeline was inspired by [11]. This pipeline utilizes the **bowtie-build** command-line tool, which is part of the Bowtie suite of tools [12]. Bowtie is designed for aligning short DNA sequencing reads to a reference genome using advanced indexing techniques such as the Burrows-Wheeler Transform.

The pipeline generates an index from a genome stored in FASTA file format [13]. The structure of the pipeline is illustrated in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Bowtie pipeline structure [11]

The *Rev_command* pipeline implements in Python the `rev` [14] Linux command applied on a file. This pipeline was meant to be like a dummy pipeline to test the conversion and have a simpler comparison pipeline.

Figure 3 presents the average execution time over five consecutive runs for the two pipelines described previously, showing that CWL is faster in execution than Mage AI, which has a large overhead, presenting the benefits of using CWL for workflow execution.

Fig. 3. Execution speed comparison between Mage AI and CWL

The source code for the experiment and all the necessary files can be found here on https://github.com/JarcauCristian/MageAPI/tree/main/mage_to_cwl/examples.

Following the performance evaluation, in which CWL came on top, an additional experiment was conducted to assess the portability of the two pipeline representations (Mage AI and CWL). Portability, in this context, refers to the ease and reliability with which pipelines can be deployed and executed across diverse computational environments, with minimal to no effort. Multiple criteria such as deployment complexity, time required for deployment, number of dependencies, compatibility with different platforms, configuration effort, reproducibility, and errors encountered were systematically compared. Table II summarizes the findings from this portability analysis across various computational scenarios.

IV. CHALLENGES ADDRESSED

In the process of bringing the Mage AI pipelines to a standardized format that is CWL, some challenges have arisen, so this section will try to go over most of the challenges encountered, explain them and, if possible, propose mitigations to solve these challenges.

TABLE II. PORTABILITY COMPARISON BETWEEN MAGE AI AND CWL

Portability Criterion	Environment	Mage AI	CWL	Notes
Deployment Complexity	General	Medium	Low	Both Mage AI and CWL support deployment via Python's pip package manager; however, Mage AI installs as a complete application with a fully featured UI, whereas CWL offers only a CLI. Additionally, the pip-based installation for Mage AI can sometimes be unreliable.
Compatibility (OS)	Linux/macOS	Full	Full	Mage AI also works natively on Windows via pip installation, while CWL requires Windows Subsystem for Linux (WSL).
Compatibility (Containers)	Docker/Containerd	Yes	Yes	Both Mage AI and CWL can work on docker, but Mage AI comes with official Docker image that is maintained by the creators.
Configuration Effort	General	Medium	Low	CWL is easy to set up, as it's simply a CLI tool for validating and executing workflows. In contrast, Mage AI is a full-fledged application requiring additional setup unrelated to workflow execution, such as user interface configuration and account management.
Reproducibility	Across Environments	Medium	High	Given that CWL can be reliably installed via pip in most environments and allows workflows to be executed with a single command, it offers a much simpler and more accessible setup to reproduce across environments. In contrast, Mage AI requires additional configuration, is unreliable when installed via pip, and typically needs to be run in a Docker container.
Errors Encountered	General	None	None	None

A. Dependency Management

One significant challenge in converting Mage AI pipelines into standalone Python scripts is their reliance on resources specific to the active Mage AI environment. Dependencies such as custom imported functions, variables, classes, configurations, or files often reside exclusively within the Mage instance and are not inherently accessible to external scripts. Consequently, generating a truly standalone Python script demands careful manual intervention, as these environment-specific dependencies cannot be resolved automatically during the conversion process.

Automated resolution of these dependencies through direct code parsing alone is exceedingly difficult due to the variability and context-specific nature of code structures. To mitigate this challenge, establishing a standardized organizational structure within the Mage AI instance is recommended. This involves placing all custom code (excluding third-party libraries) and associated resources, such as configuration files, scripts, and supporting data files, into clearly defined, dedicated directories within the Mage environment.

By adhering to this standardized structure, the script conversion process can systematically and efficiently identify all dependencies. The process involves scanning these predefined directories to locate and extract relevant file paths, imported modules, and associated resources. This structured approach greatly simplifies dependency management, enabling automated tools to bundle all necessary resources accurately and efficiently.

In practice, this means:

- 1) Clearly defining directories within Mage AI for custom modules, scripts, and resource files.
- 2) Ensuring that all internally referenced code and files within Mage pipelines follow this standardized organization.
- 3) Implementing a scanning mechanism during the conversion process to automatically detect and include these resources.

Adopting this methodology not only simplifies the conversion of Mage pipelines into standalone scripts but also enhances reproducibility and maintainability. The consolidated archive generated through this approach ensures completeness, enabling seamless execution of the workflow outside the original Mage AI environment, particularly within CWL (Common Workflow Language) workflows.

B. Error Handling

While the current implementation successfully transforms most Mage AI pipelines, certain Mage-specific scenarios remain difficult to replicate in CWL. In addition, unforeseen corner cases may arise that require extensive testing to identify. These cases can lead to code failures in its CWL form. Resolving such issues currently requires manual intervention to execute the code, diagnose failures, and implement fixes. Although this process cannot be fully automated at present, advancements in AI and large language models (LLMs) may,

in the future, enable automated static analysis of the code to predict its functionality and address potential errors. Some studies have already started addressing this issue, with [15] conducting experiments on rewriting and optimizing Python code using LLMs.

C. Data Visualization

Another challenge that was encountered while developing the solution was data visualization, especially figures and images that are created alongside the workflow because they need to be identified at the point of conversion and then code should be added to save them for later visualization. Data visualization introduces an additional challenge in debugging. When the workflow is executed, outputs such as print statements are not displayed on the screen, making it more difficult to identify and diagnose potential errors.

An approach to addressing the issue of data visualization, which is partially implemented in the current solution, involves saving all variables that can be serialized in the pickle format [16] into a pickle file. A separate script can then be used to display these variables in a user-friendly manner. Currently, this functionality is only implemented for the final step in the workflow but can be extended to include all steps in the pipeline, providing a broader view of what is happening to the data alongside the workflow.

The debugging challenge can be mitigated by generating a log file during the workflow's execution. However, users must manually add the logging of information relevant to their needs to ensure effective debugging.

V. APPLICATIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This methodology has several practical applications and paves the way for future research and development, as it facilitates:

- Seamless integration of Mage workflows into cloud-based environments. They can leverage cloud-based platforms like Kubernetes and TESK [7], to ensure robust execution and monitoring.
- Enhanced reproducibility and portability of data pipelines. With workflows standardized in CWL and Python, researchers and organizations can share and reproduce pipelines across different teams and computational environments.
- Future extensions to support additional workflow standards. The methodology supports the broader adoption of workflow-oriented standards, making it easier for organizations to comply with industry and regulatory requirements.

Potential future work on the proposed methodology may include:

- Optimization of the transformation process by improving the efficiency and the accuracy of the transformation algorithms. This can be implemented by reducing computational overhead and addressing edge cases that may arise in complex workflows.

- Advanced error handling and validation mechanisms. Build more robust error detection and correction tools to enhance the reliability of the transformation process.
- Integration with MLOps pipelines in future iterations. This could integrate the transformation methodology into MLOps pipelines, enabling seamless transitions from data preprocessing to model deployment.

VI. CONCLUSION

By transforming Mage workflows into CWL and Python standards, this methodology bridges the gap between user-friendly pipeline design and industry-standard execution. Future work includes optimizing the transformation process and extending support for additional standards. Other workflow systems, such as Apache Airflow and Nextflow, offer powerful orchestration and scalability features but often come with significant overhead and complexity in configuration. For instance, Airflow's Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG)-based execution requires users to write detailed YAML configurations, which can be a barrier for less experienced users. Similarly, Nextflow excels in managing complex, bioinformatics-focused workflows but is tightly coupled with its domain-specific syntax. In contrast, CWL provides a standardized and portable framework that ensures workflows are executable across diverse environments without additional configuration burdens. As demonstrated in the experimental results, CWL workflows achieve faster execution compared to Mage AI, largely due to their reduced overhead and streamlined architecture.

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